
Series: PHYSICS

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Radiation of a uniformly moving charge

Annotation

It is generally accepted that a uniformly moving charge does not radiate. At the same time, Cherenkov-Vavilov radiation is known, which arises in a medium (but not in a vacuum), when a charge moves at a speed exceeding the speed of light in this medium. The energy for such radiation is extracted from the medium under the action of a particle moving in it. Below we will consider the rectilinear and uniform motion of a charge that moves in a vacuum and which has no other source of energy other than its own kinetic energy. It will be shown that from Maxwell's equations a solution follows that describes the radiation of such a charge.

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1. Introduction

It is generally accepted that a uniformly moving charge does not radiate. At the same time, it is known that a uniformly moving charge emits in a medium (but not in a vacuum) - this is Cherenkov-Vavilov radiation, which is experimentally observed when a charge moves with a speed (in a medium) exceeding the speed of light in this medium. This radiation is explained as radiation of the medium under the action of a particle moving in it [1].

Below we will consider the rectilinear and uniform motion of a charge that moves in a vacuum and which has no other source of energy other than its own kinetic energy. It will be shown that from Maxwell's equations a solution follows that describes the radiation of such a charge.

In [4] the author showed that there is a solution of Maxwell's equations for a charge that moves uniformly in a vacuum and does NOT radiate. It will be shown below that there is also a solution of Maxwell's equations for a charge that moves uniformly in a vacuum and radiates at the same time. Apparently, both cases are really possible.

2. Statement of the problem

Here we will use the method for solving Maxwell's equations proposed in [3]. The Maxwell equations in the CGS system of the following form are considered:

$$\text{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$\text{rot}(H) + \frac{4\pi}{c} J - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = 0, \tag{2}$$

$$\text{div}(E) = 4\pi\rho, \tag{3}$$

$$\text{div}(H) = 0, \tag{4}$$

where

H, E is magnetic and electrical strengths, respectively,

J is current density,

ρ is the charge density.

We will use cylindrical coordinates r, ϕ, z , and consider the movement of charge q along the oz axis. We will denote as z_0, z the current, and analyzed coordinates of the point, respectively. The charge v is located at the point z_0 , therefore the charge density is determined through the delta function, i.e.

$$\rho = q \cdot \delta(z_0 - z), \tag{5}$$

$$J = v\rho, \tag{6}$$

where v is the speed of the charge.

To shorten the notation, we will further use the following notation:

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi \cdot \delta(z_0 - z)), \tag{7}$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi \cdot \delta(z_0 - z)), \tag{8}$$

where α, χ are some constants. The derivatives of these functions with respect to z have the form

$$b_{\text{co}} = -\chi, \tag{9}$$

$$b_{\text{si}} = \chi. \tag{10}$$

We represent the unknown functions in the following form:

$$H_r = h_r(r)\text{co}, \tag{11}$$

$$H_\phi = h_\phi(r)\text{si}, \tag{12}$$

$$H_z = h_z(r)\text{si}, \tag{13}$$

$$E_r = e_r(r)si, \tag{14}$$

$$E_\phi = e_\phi(r)c\phi, \tag{15}$$

$$E_z = e_z(r)c\phi, \tag{16}$$

where

- E_r, E_ϕ, E_z is electrical strengths,
- H_r, H_ϕ, H_z is magnetic strengths,
- $h(r), e(r)$ are some functions of coordinate r ,

A rigorous proof that Maxwell's equations with electric charges defined by the delta function can be represented in this form is given in [2, Sections 6, 9.6.7].

In the system of cylindrical coordinates, equations (1-4) are:

$$\frac{E_r}{r} + \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = 4\pi\rho, \tag{17}$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_r}{dt}, \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{\partial E_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial r} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_\phi}{dt}, \tag{19}$$

$$\frac{E_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{dH_z}{dt}, \tag{20}$$

$$\frac{H_r}{r} + \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \tag{21}$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_r}{dt}, \tag{22}$$

$$\frac{\partial H_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial r} = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_\phi}{dt}, \tag{23}$$

$$\frac{H_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial \phi} + \frac{4\pi}{c} J = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{dE_z}{dt}. \tag{24}$$

By direct substitution, one can make sure that functions (11-16) transform the system of equations (17-24) with four arguments r, ϕ, z, t into a system of equations with one argument r and unknown functions $h(r), e(r)$. This system of equations is as follows:

$$\frac{e_r(r)}{r} + e'_r(r) - \frac{e_\phi(r)}{r} \alpha - \chi \cdot e_z(r) - \frac{4\pi}{\varepsilon} \rho = 0, \tag{25}$$

$$-\frac{1}{r} \cdot e_z(r) \alpha + \chi \cdot e_\phi(r) - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_r = 0, \tag{26}$$

$$e_r(r) \chi - e'_z(r) + \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_\phi = 0, \tag{27}$$

$$\frac{e_\phi(r)}{r} + e'_\phi(r) - \frac{e_r(r)}{r} \cdot \alpha + \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_z = 0, \tag{28}$$

$$\frac{h_r(r)}{r} + h'_r(r) + \frac{h_\phi(r)}{r} \alpha - \chi \cdot h_z(r) = 0, \tag{29}$$

$$\frac{1}{r} h_z(r) \propto -\chi h_\phi(r) - \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_r(r) = 0, \tag{30}$$

$$h_r(r) b_{si} - \dot{h}_z(r) + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_\phi(r) = 0, \tag{31}$$

$$\frac{h_\varphi(r)}{r} + \dot{h}_\varphi(r) + \frac{-h_r(r)}{r} \alpha + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_z(r) + \frac{4\pi}{c} J = 0. \quad (32)$$

We will seek a solution to these equations under the assumption that

$$h_r = ke_r, \quad (33)$$

$$h_\varphi = -ke_\varphi, \quad (34)$$

$$h_z = -ke_z. \quad (35)$$

In [3, Chapter 2] it is shown that in this case the energy flux densities satisfy the energy conservation law.

We change the variables according to (33-35) in equations (25-32) and rewrite them:

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_\varphi}{r} \alpha - \chi e_z - \frac{4\pi}{\varepsilon} \rho = 0, \quad (36)$$

$$-\frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + \chi e_\varphi - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} ke_r = 0, \quad (37)$$

$$-\dot{e}_z + \chi e_r - k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_\varphi = 0, \quad (38)$$

$$\frac{e_\varphi}{r} + \dot{e}_\varphi - \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha - k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_z = 0, \quad (39)$$

$$k \frac{e_r}{r} + k \dot{e}_r - k \frac{e_\varphi}{r} \alpha - k \chi e_z = 0, \quad (40)$$

$$-k \frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + k \chi e_\varphi - \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_r = 0, \quad (41)$$

$$k \dot{e}_z - k \chi e_r + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_\varphi = 0, \quad (42)$$

$$-k \frac{e_\varphi}{r} - k \dot{e}_\varphi + k \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_z + \frac{4\pi}{c} J = 0. \quad (43)$$

This system of equations takes on different forms for different values of z. Let's consider the solution of these systems of equations.

3. Solution at $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}_0$

In this case, we have:

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_\varphi}{r} \alpha + \chi e_z - 4\pi\rho = 0, \quad (44)$$

$$-\frac{e_z}{r} \alpha - \chi e_\varphi - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} ke_r = 0, \quad (45)$$

$$-\dot{e}_z - k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_\varphi = 0, \quad (46)$$

$$+\frac{e_\varphi}{r} + \dot{e}_\varphi - \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha - k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_z = 0, \quad (47)$$

$$k \frac{e_r}{r} + k \dot{e}_r - k \frac{e_\varphi}{r} \alpha + k \chi e_z = 0, \quad (48)$$

$$-k \frac{e_z}{r} \alpha - \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_r = 0, \quad (49)$$

$$k \dot{e}_z + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_\varphi = 0, \quad (50)$$

$$-k \frac{e_\varphi}{r} - k \dot{e}_\varphi + k \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_z + \frac{4\pi}{c} J = 0. \quad (51)$$

Note that equations (44) and (51) coincide for

$$\frac{4\pi}{c}J = -k \frac{4\pi}{\varepsilon}\rho, \tag{52}$$

$$\frac{\varepsilon\omega}{kc} = \chi, \tag{53}$$

It follows from (52) and (6) that

$$\frac{4\pi}{c}v\rho = -k \frac{4\pi}{\varepsilon}\rho \tag{54}$$

or

$$k = -\frac{v\varepsilon}{c}. \tag{55}$$

It follows from (53) and (55) that

$$\chi = -\frac{\omega}{v}. \tag{56}$$

4. Solution at $\mathbf{z} \neq \mathbf{z}_0$

In this case, we have:

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_\varphi}{r}\alpha - \chi e_z = 0, \tag{57}$$

$$-\frac{e_z}{r}\alpha + \chi e_\varphi - \frac{\mu\omega}{c}ke_r = 0, \tag{58}$$

$$-\dot{e}_z + b_{si}e_r - k\frac{\mu\omega}{c}e_\varphi = 0, \tag{59}$$

$$\frac{e_\varphi}{r} + \dot{e}_\varphi - \frac{e_r}{r}\alpha - k\frac{\mu\omega}{c}e_z = 0, \tag{60}$$

$$k\frac{e_r}{r} + k\dot{e}_r - k\frac{e_\varphi}{r}\alpha - k\chi e_z = 0, \tag{61}$$

$$-k\frac{e_z}{r}\alpha + k\chi e_\varphi - \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c}e_r = 0, \tag{62}$$

$$k\dot{e}_z - k\chi e_r + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c}e_\varphi = 0, \tag{63}$$

$$-k\frac{e_\varphi}{r} - k\dot{e}_\varphi + k\frac{e_r}{r}\alpha + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c}e_z = 0. \tag{64}$$

Note that equations (58) and (62) coincide for

$$\frac{\varepsilon\omega}{kc} = \frac{\mu\omega k}{c}. \tag{65}$$

Under the same condition, equations (60) and (64) coincide, as well as equations (59, 63). Equations (57) and (61) coincide under condition (55). Finally, equations (64) and (68) coincide. Thus, equations (62, 64, 63, 61) can be excluded from the system of equations and replaced by conditions (65, 55). The remaining 4 equations (57-60) are a system of differential equations with 3 unknowns.

The solution to this overdetermined system of equations exists for

$$e_z = 0. \tag{66}$$

Moreover, from (57, 60) we find

$$e_\varphi = e_r. \tag{67}$$

From (57, 66, 67) we find:

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha = 0 \tag{68}$$

or

$$e_\varphi = e_r = Ar^{\alpha-1}, \tag{69}$$

where A is the amplitude of the strength.

The frequency in this solution is not fixed. Consequently, the charge can radiate with any frequency.

5. Energy flows

In [3, Chapter 2] it is shown that under conditions of the form (7, 8, 33, 34, 35), the energy flux densities are determined by the formulas

$$S_r = 0, \tag{70}$$

$$S_\varphi = \eta k e_r e_z, \tag{71}$$

$$S_z = \eta k e_r e_\varphi, \tag{72}$$

$$\eta = c/4\pi, \tag{73}$$

i.e. there is no radial energy flux, and the energy flux densities at a given radius along the circumference and along the vertical do not depend on time and other coordinates. This means that the wave emitted by the charge carries away the energy flux with a density

$$S = 2\eta k e_r e_\varphi. \tag{74}$$

6. Conclusions

Obviously, this flux with density (74) is the power *P* with which the kinetic energy of the charge is consumed, and, therefore, the speed of its movement decreases. In this case, the amplitude of the tensions also decreases. Hence,

if an electric charge moves in a medium with a certain constant speed, then it emits an electromagnetic wave, the amplitude of which decreases with time.

So, the obtained solution describes the motion of the charge *q* in the medium (*μ*, *ε*) with a certain speed *v*. With this strengths

$$H_r = h_r(r) \text{co}, \tag{11}$$

$$H_\phi = h_\phi(r) \text{si}, \tag{12}$$

$$E_r = e_r(r) \text{si}, \tag{14}$$

$$E_\phi = e_\phi(r) \text{co}, \tag{15}$$

where

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi \cdot \delta(z_o - z)), \tag{7}$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi \cdot \delta(z_o - z)), \tag{8}$$

$$e_\varphi = e_r = Ar^{\alpha-1}, \quad (69)$$

$$h_r = ke_r, \quad (33)$$

$$h_\varphi = -ke_\varphi, \quad (34)$$

$$k = -\frac{v\varepsilon}{c}, \quad (55)$$

$$\chi = -\frac{\omega}{v}. \quad (56)$$

References

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